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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 4.9 – CONCEPT OF VIRTUAL USER INTERFACE (FINAL VERSION)

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Executive summary

This deliverable 4.9 is a demonstrator (DEM) presentation. The deliverable is the final and updated version of the deliverable D4.5 presenting the concepts of virtual user interfaces and the state of simulation solutions in connection to task *T4.5 Simulation based interaction* in which the goal is to utilize simulation and simulator as a platform to evaluate new user interface solutions. The selected interaction concepts identified in the project are implemented in a simulated environment. The internal states of the simulated models are used to simulate sensor data based on which interaction concepts are controlled.

The focus is on user interactions with the simulated machine operating in a virtual environment. There are dedicated simulators for each of the use cases. The UC1 and UC3 simulators are developed by CREA and both have the capabilities of the Creanex simulator platform. The UC2 simulator is developed by VTT. Game engine graphics are used for visualization and to test XR visualization features. Physics simulation for the work machines of the use cases, snow groomer, reach stacker and excavator, are implemented to enable development, evaluation and testing in virtual environments. The development of the UC1 and UC3 simulators has continued actively since the first version of the deliverable 4.5. The simulator of UC2 had already the planned features implemented and described in the first version, and it has been used to gather feedback from actual end users as reported in the deliverable *3.9 – Low-Fidelity XR Prototypes (Final Version)*.

The table of contents follows the first version with couple of changes. A brief description of the user interfaces of the work machines is separated into its own chapter 2, followed by the chapter 3 of general description of the use case simulators and their capabilities. The rest of the deliverable follows the structure of the first version with added sub-chapters describing the developments done. Chapter 4 has presentations of the virtual user interfaces and sensors that were implemented for the use cases 1 and 3.

In the deliverable *D2.5 Technology analysis and requirements specification (final version)* scenarios of the use cases are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The virtual feedback visualizations are based on scenario requirements and identified interaction between the mobile machinery and the human operator. The concepts of the feedback visualizations, which were foreseen to be added and have been implemented to simulations, are presented for each use case in chapter 5.

The simulations developed for the use cases provide a platform to integrate concepts developed in WP3-WP5 into the virtual environment for early testing and demonstration in WP6. The simulated versions enable testing and evaluation of the concepts safely and economically. Another advantage is that the test scenario can be saved and used multiple times to obtain comparable results.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable is a demonstrator presentation and presents the concepts of virtual user interfaces which simulate the ideas identified as potential new user interface solutions. Implementing ideas first in a simulated environment enables evaluation and discussion of the features in early state and feedback can be collected in a safe operating environment. Simulators have the advantage that simulation can be done all year round. Real life tests are vital to understand all aspects of machine operation in changing conditions, but using simulation tools throughout the project is very cost effective compared to arranging test days with real equipment. Simulated user interface solutions also provide opportunities to test ideas which might not yet be feasible to implement in practice but could be enabled by new technologies foreseen.

The user interface of a machine can be divided into control inputs and feedback information. The user interface elements that are common and conventional in present day work machines are shortly presented in chapter 2. Input devices used for controlling a machine are typically joysticks, pedals and switches or push buttons. Feedback information is presented on monitors and by indicators lights for example.

In task T4.5 simulators are used to evaluate new user interface solutions. The selected interaction concepts identified in the project have been implemented in a simulated environment and there are dedicated simulators for each of the use cases. The simulators and their capabilities are presented in the chapter 3. Game engine graphics are used for visualization and to test XR visualization features. Physics simulation for the work machines of the use cases, snow groomer, reach stacker and excavator, are implemented to enable development, evaluation and testing in virtual environments. The UC1 and UC3 simulators are developed by CREA and both have the capabilities of the Creanex simulator platform. The UC2 simulator is developed by VTT.

In section 4.1 examples of creating virtual counterparts for control panels are presented for machines of cases 1 and 3. Real control panels are not always practical to arrange for all who are using a simulator for different purposes. Virtual panels are software, so they can also be controlled by software to simulate user actions as a test case.

To be able to give feedback, to show more information and to control the machine in a way which considers the non-perceivable state, situational information and measured data are needed. The advantage in simulation is that additional information is available from the model and this information can be used to evaluate extended feedback features cost effectively before trying those with real machines. In section 4.2 an example solution is presented to create configurable sensor signals for machine joints and part positions based on the kinematic structure of a machine.

Examples of visualization technics and simulation solutions for each use case are presented in section 5 including concept ideas for virtual feedback visualizations.

2 User interfaces of work machines

The user interface can be divided into two main parts:

- control interface,
- feedback interface

The operator uses the control devices to give commands to the work machine. The state of the machine and measured sensor data are given as feedback to the operator, see Figure 1.

Figure 1: General structure of user interface.

Control interfaces may have several different kinds of devices. The most used ones are conventional controls like joysticks, switches, keys, push buttons, wheels and pedals.

New technologies have made it possible to add more sophisticated controls like gesture controls based on camera input and voice controls with microphone and speech recognition.

Those are not yet common in work machines, but they are getting common in consumer market.

Feedback interface may also be a combination of multiple devices, such as display monitors, indicator lights and sound speakers.

Some of the user interface devices can be hybrid ones having both control and feedback features: such as touchscreens or control joystick with haptic feedback.

In Figure 2 a typical current user interface of excavators is shown. The boom and bucket movements are controlled by X-Y joysticks having push buttons and proportional sliders and the 3D model of the excavation target with measurement data are shown in a touchscreen.

Figure 2: Example of a typical user interface in a work machine, case excavator.

Cameras are also very common feedback channel nowadays, for example to show rear view or other areas that cannot otherwise be seen from the cabin. Using multiple cameras, a 360-degree top view can be presented for the operator and additional lines and symbols can be added on top of the video for additional information like how a car would turn based on steering. Examples are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Camera based parking assistance with AR type of additional helpers.

In a simulated environment it is also possible to simulate video streams. An additional rendering camera can be created in the visual system and rendered images are packed to a video stream.

The geographical location of the operated machine is important feedback information as well. There are many types of systems and devices on the market to measure geographical location. Different manufacturers might have their own proprietary interfaces, but it is very common that location information is available in standard NMEA through a serial or ethernet connection. Creanex simulator supports multiple standard NMEA messages (GGA, RMC, HDT, GSV, GSA, GNS, GMP and VTG [2]) and some manufacturer specific ones of Trimble and Leica (PJK, LLL and LLQ).

Forces acting in parts of a work machine are typically measured from hydraulic cylinder by pressure transducers. Movement simulation is based on available forces, but actual measured forces and pressures

come from the counter force from dynamic and environment interactions. In some cases, the load pressure can be well simulated and in some it is more challenging.

Summary of Creanex simulator feedback channels is presented on Figure 4.

Figure 4: Examples of feedback information in Creanex simulators.

3 Simulators and their capabilities

Creanex simulator platform, which provides a rich set of features and building blocks to develop a simulator, is utilized in snow grooming and construction use cases 1 and 3. A top level architecture and capabilities of Creanex simulators are presented in section 3.1. The reach stacker simulator of use case 2 is developed by VTT and it is presented in section 3.2.

3.1 UC1 snow groomer and UC3 excavator simulators

The UC1 snow groomer and UC3 excavator simulator are built on top of the Creanex simulator platform. The snow groomer simulation has been developed during the THEIA^{XR} project. For the excavator simulation CREA had a previous simulation which has been updated to better support the project requirement like the physics simulation of the excavator and the excavation itself. Simulators have been developed, and features have been added so that the THEIA^{XR} concepts can be tested and demonstrated on both simulators. Project partners have been given licenses of the simulator software, so they can use the simulators on their own and utilize them in their demos and evaluation tests. For example, HdM is planning to set up a lab-based demonstrator using the Creanex simulation for evaluation and demonstration purposes.

A couple of the platform features are presented in sections 3.1.2–3.1.3 as those are especially useful in THEIA^{XR} simulators. The framework of the virtual control panels is also a platform feature used in the project and examples are presented in chapter 4.1.

3.1.1 General capabilities

The main parts of the Creanex simulator structure are

- real or virtualized controls and interfaces for them,
- simulation model, its dynamics and signal interface,
- visualization application,
- visualization media

The Creanex simulator architecture can be divided into layers. At the bottom are the interfaces to external IO devices. The physical controls are typically connected by an IO card or a device having CAN bus interface. Simulator has support for multiple type of IO cards connected by USB and CAN interfaces for CANopen and J1939 nodes. Virtual CAN nodes are also used to simulate for example encoders, inclinometers, pressure transducers and above all a diesel engine. There are also interfaces to external applications. The crnxTesting is interface to Python applications and SimLabLink is interface to MathWorks SimuLink[®] and Matlab[®]. One the unique ones is the crnxSoftPLC, which has support for virtual CAN bus and IO channels connected to a virtual counter part of an embedded control unit. Creanex simulator platform contains multi-purpose simulation objects from which the application implementation is derived. The layered structure is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: General architecture of Creanex simulators.

In Creanex simulators the simulation and visualization have separate applications connected by ethernet communication. This has the benefit that there can be multiple visualizations running in separate computers showing a view from different direction or location. Extra visual channel can also be used for generating virtual video streams.

Simulation is series of sub-step that are executed in a loop having fixed time step, typically 20 ms. First the control inputs are measured, and then the raw values are converted to simulation signals, which are further on connected to the simulated machine model. After each simulation step, the new state is sent to the visual application and values of the virtual sensors are updates, see Figure 6. A value of a virtual sensor can be connected to an IO card, CAN message, UDP message and or to the visual to update some augmented visual element.

Figure 6: Creanex simulator applications and IO connection to simulation model.

Creanex simulators have been and are used in many R&D projects. One of the key capabilities is the wide support for control system development and testing. Creanex simulators support both hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) and software-in-the-loop type of simulations (SIL). Creanex technology scales well and there are solutions having only one ECU and some has a dozen ECUs which run code under development and testing. In addition to ECUs there is often many more third-party CAN nodes which are simulated by virtual counterparts.

Simulation is executed in real time. Typically, the IO interface is updated every 10 ms and the dynamic models every 20 ms. Dynamic simulation uses special physics engine which enables interactions with the environment meaning excavator can dig the soil and with a grapple crane one can manipulate objects for example.

Creanex has developed special IO card which can be directly connected to ECU input and output pins. Couple of key features are the electronically simulated feedback current for PWM controls and quadrature encoders.

The virtual control panels and sensors for machine kinematic structure were already presented in sections 4.1 and 4.2. Other capabilities are

- Multiple type of IO cards to connect control panels and ECUs to simulation,
- Configurable signal interface of the simulated models,
- Multi-threaded rigid-body dynamics,
- Support for virtual diesel engine,
- Support for J1939 protocol and virtual nodes based on it,
- Support for CANopen protocol and multiple virtual nodes based CiA device profiles,
- crnxTesting interface for test cases in Python language,
- SimLabLink interface for the Mathworks software products,
- simulated GNSS,
- UDP based IO and signal interface for third party applications,
- Visualization based on Unity game engine.

Creanex simulator platform supports also a motion base. The standard version has two degrees of freedom. The upper frame can tilt around 10 degrees in forward-backwards direction and sideways. Motion of the platform is quite essential in some application like operating an excavator. Having a feeling of the machine movements and inclination increases the realism of the simulation. The photo in the Figure 7 was taken during the Tampere consortium meeting in June 2024 when the first version of the snow groomer simulation was presented and tested by the project's partners.

Figure 7: Creanex 2 dof motion platform and snow groomer simulation.

3.1.2 CAN interface

CAN bus and messaging has been selected in THEIA^{XR} as the primary communication method between systems in UC1 and UC3. Controlling joystick have CAN interface and the systems developed by partners are also capable of receiving data as CAN messages. Creanex simulator platform has support for Kvaser CAN adapters (<https://kvaser.com/>) and for the CANopen protocol stack including configurable CANopen slave and master nodes, which convert CAN messages to simulator IO channels and vice versa, see Figure 8.

Figure 8: CAN interface of the Creanex simulator platform.

The CAN nodes of the simulator are said to be virtual as they are simulated versions and to distinguish them from the real CANopen devices. The nodes are configured in a text file, the format of which is the Device Configuration File (DCF) standardized by CiA [3].

3.1.3 Animated objects on work site

One of the important goals in the project has been to make persons around a working machine perceivable. Two animated characters were added to visualization media. Alpin skier was purchased from the TurboSquid 3D model store ([3D Model Real-time Rigged Winter Sports - TurboSquid 1232639](https://www.turbosquid.com/3D-Model-Real-time-Rigged-Winter-Sports-TurboSquid-1232639)) and modified to be compatible Creanex platform animations feature. A walking worker was created using assets that can be download from <https://www.mixamo.com/>. The animated skier and worker are presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Animated skier and worker.

The simulators UC1 and UC3 have a user interface tool to add the selected animated object into the simulated scene and to define a path the object moves.

3.2 UC2 reach stacker simulator

The reach stacker simulator was developed by VTT. All planned and implemented features were documented in the first version of this deliverable and after that the simulator has already been used to gather feedback from the actual end users.

The application is built using Unity game engine, which supports high quality graphics and built in physics simulation engine (Figure 10).

Figure 10: VTT simulator hardware setup.

The hardware setup (Figure 10) VTT uses for the reach stacker simulation consists of three wall-sized screens, placed with an angle of 120° between each other, Figure 11. The total screen resolution available is 5760x1200 pixels, and the full size of the screens is used to show real-time camera footage from several 360° cameras placed both on the vehicle and on key location of the logistic hub. As input devices, the demo makes use of a Logitech Extreme 3D joystick for controlling the reach stacker’s boom and spreader, and an Ultraleap Stereo IR 170 hand-tracking device for controlling the camera views and their position on the screen. A keyboard is also used for handling simulation aspects (such as changing the weather from rain to snow, etc.), and for proving specific commands that were not bound to any of the other peripherals (such as disabling one or both of the AR load charts).

Figure 11: Reach stacker research simulator in VTT simulation environment.

In simulation it is convenient to study different choices for camera views. Currently the test design has four views as shown in Figure 12:

- 1) cabin view/driver's perspective,
- 2) spreader top-down view,
- 3) rear view/counterweight, and
- 4) drone/bird's eye view.

Augmented content is based on several available sensors and other data and the content can be camera view specific.

Figure 12: Reachstacker simulator with four parallel camera views.

The demo intentionally includes a high number of features available to the user, to study which ones are felt to be the most useful and help the operator to do container handling better. The features are described later in chapter 5.3.

Other capabilities are

- support for the Haption Virtuose 6D haptic control device,
- virtual weight sensor,
- virtual inertial measurement unit,
- weather simulation (wind strength and direction, temperature, humidity),
- virtual LIDAR sensor and
- support for Varjo XR3 headset.

Varjo XR-3 headset supports video pass through technology, which allows users to see the actual remote operation station and virtual representation of the reach stacker and harbour environment all at the same time. A screen capture of the test setup is presented in Figure 13. The video pass through works well and it can be used merge AR content with the real time video. Currently the Varjo headset is quite heavy and is not suited to be used for longer time periods or is not at least ergonomic for that. Technology was tested but will not be included in demonstrations.

Figure 13: Varjo XR3 headset is capable to merge real time video with rendered graphics view.

4 Virtual user interface

A virtual user interface is a simulated version of a real one or it can be also a simulated version of a new user interface concept, which is first tested in a virtual environment.

The Creanex simulator platform has support to virtualize the control devices of the machine user interface like joysticks, switches and push buttons. The solution is to have a window with configured widgets for the control elements. In section 4.1 a general overview is first presented how the of the virtual control panels can be configured. The sub-section 4.1.1 presents the solution implemented for the Prinoth Leitwolf snow groomer controls and the sub-section 4.1.2 presents the solution for the excavator controls.

Section 4.2 presents some considerations for virtualizing sensors, including one Creanex implementation, used to measure a state of a machine and to provide feedback for the operator.

4.1 Virtualization of control panels

A control panel can be virtualized on a display monitor as a window having control widgets. This type of virtualization is available on the Creanex simulator platform and can be taken in use in different type of simulator implementations.

Virtualization makes it possible to have the same set of controls in a simulator without any real physical control devices. Of course, having a real cabin or an identical mock-up with all machine controls is authentic operating environment, which has many advantages. If, for example, experienced operators are brought to a simulator, so that they can evaluate and give feedback of the implemented features then it is better to have a similar operating cabin to which they are used to. A realistic simulation can also be controlled by virtual counterparts of real controls on a touch screen. This way the simulator can be cost effectively made available for larger audience and used by different stage holders and project partners.

The virtual user interface panel is available in Creanex simulator platform utilized in use cases 1 and 3. The virtual panel is a window, which can be operated with a mouse or touch screen. The content is configured in a text file having MS INI file format. A user can add named control objects on defined locations of the window. For each control a type is configured and attributes that depend on the selected control type. For example, a control panel could have a X-Y joystick and a rotary switch. A virtual counterpart would be a window which are two active areas, one for each control. Each active area has a picture which also indicates in which state a control is. In addition, there can be a toolbar to record user actions and to playback recording afterwards.

Figure 14: Example of virtual panel having conventional controls.

The following configuration example shows how the example Figure 14 is configured. First the controls are named in section [UIControls] and then each control is configured in a section named accordingly. The X-Y joystick is named as LeftJoystick, and the two-state rotating switch is named as PowerSwitch.

```
[UIControls]
*Control = LeftJoystick
*Control = BtnStart

[LeftJoystick]
Position = 20 20
Size = 250 250
Name = Crane forward/backward and left/right
Type = JOYSTICK
Image = JoyStickCrosshair.png
Channel1 = IODeviceOfJS LeftJSX
Channel2 = IODeviceOfJS LeftJSY
Horizontal_X = -1024 1023
Horizontal_Y = -100 100
Vertical_X = -1024 1023
Vertical_Y = -100 100

[PowerSwitch]
Position = 20 300
Size = 50 50
Name = PowerSW
Type = BUTTON_ROTARY
RotaryBandStart = 0
RotaryBandRange = 90
PositionCount = 2
Image1 = PowerSwitch-Off.png
Image2 = PowerSwitch-On.png
Staydown = 1 1
Channel1 =
Channel2 = IODeviceOfDashboard PowerSW
```

The graphical object of the joystick showing the active area of the control is JoyStickCrosshair.png set in parameter image, Figure 15. The control position of the joystick is shown by a round dot on top of the background picture, see Figure 14. Joystick position is converted to output value by the Horizontal and Vertical scaling parameters, which define a piecewise line curve by set of value pairs. After scaling the resulting output value is updated to connected IO device defined by Channel1 parameter.

Figure 15: Background picture for a virtual X-Y joystick.

The number of rotary positions or states a switch can have, is defined by the parameters PositionCount. The PowerSwitch of the example has two states, so two background pictures are defined, Image1 and Image2, shown in Figure 16. Each state has also IO channel and the one of the active state is set on. The parameters RotaryBandStart and RotaryBandRange define sector area to select an active state.

Figure 16: Background pictures for a virtual rotary switch.

There are support for multiple different type of conventional controls used in work machine user interfaces, see table.

Type	Description
BUTTON_PUSH	Push button
BUTTON_HORIZONTAL	Horizontal rocker switch
BUTTON_VERTICAL	Vertical rocker switch
BUTTON_ROTARY	Rotary switch with positions along circumference
BUTTON_ROTARY_ENCODER	Rotary switch having up and down steps in output value
JOYSTICK	Two or single axis joystick
BAR_WIDGET	A bar changing length according to value
VALUE_DISPLAY	Numerical value display

Table 1: Supported control types of virtual panel.

4.1.1 Virtual control panels for the UC1 snow groomer simulator

The Prinoth Leitwolf snow groomer has two levers for the left hand to controls the tracks and one multifunction joystick for the right hand. A virtual panel was configured for both ones.

The panels are opened from the view menu of the simulation application (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Virtual panels are opened from the view menu of the simulator application.

The panel of the track controls is presented in Figure 18. For both levers there is vertical slider.

The panel of the multifunction joystick is presented in Figure 19. The joystick has in total

- Two X-Y joysticks, the main handle and a small one on top part of it.
- Two rotary trimmers.
- Four two directional switches.
- Two four directional switches.
- Eight push buttons.

One or more IO channels are connected to each control element depending on the type of the element and which functions of the control element are used in the real machine. When the virtual control is used, the priority of the associated IO channel is increased to override the value of the IO channel. This way the actual control is switched from the source of the IO channel to the virtual control panel. The override state is highlighted in the simulator application with the icon

Figure 18: Virtual track controls of the snow groomer simulator.

Figure 19: Virtual right hand side control joystick of the snow groomer simulator.

The track levers and the multifunction joystick are connected to the simulator via the CAN bus. Two virtual CANopen nodes are configured to parse CAN messages data to the nodes' IO channels. The concept is presented in Figure 8: *CAN interface of the Creanex simulator platform*. The IO channels are further connected to the simulation model. The control functions of the snow groomer are presented in the deliverable 4.8 – *Interaction concepts (final version)*

4.1.2 Virtual control panels for the UC3 excavator simulator

The virtual control panels of the excavator simulator are configured for SVAB joysticks (<https://svab.se/en/modal/l8/>) used in the Creanex motion platform (Figure 7). The same works also for the Danfoss CAN bus joysticks used in the TUD cabin mock-up. Only the names of the IO channels need to be changed in the configuration.

The virtual control panel of the excavator is shown in Figure 20. Both left and right joysticks have

- X-Y channels of the handle.
- Two proportional sliders.
- Five push buttons

The main handles control the upper frame rotation, boom and bucket. The front sliders are controlling the tracks and the rear sliders are for the roto tilt movement: bucket rotation and sideways tilt. The support jacks and blade of the simulated wheeled excavator are controlled by the push buttons.

Figure 20: Virtual control joysticks of the excavator simulator.

4.2 Virtualization of sensors and feedback

Feedback given for the operator to guide and help him or her to operate the machine is based on measured data of sensors. There are several different type sensors, and the most common ones used in work machines are sensors for

- pressure of hydraulic oil or compressed air,
- angle or velocity of a rotary joint,
- position or velocity of a linear joint,
- inclination relative to gravity,
- temperature and
- surrounding clearances around a machine.

A simulated virtual model of a machine has a state based on which the sensors are simulated. For example, parts of a boom are joined together, and a virtual angle sensor is added to measure the angle between the parts, or an inclination sensor is measuring the frame orientation relative to gravity.

Sensor information is often merged into derived information which is then feedback for the operator. Based on the kinematic model of a machine and measured joint values the position of the tip of the boom can be calculated and the feedback could be warned if there is a stability risk. The simulation model may also contain special implementations for more advanced sensors like detection of objects in the vicinity of the machine. In simulation the detection can be simply a calculation of the relative position of objects. To simulate actual sensors the information for surrounding clearances can be simulated by raytracing or based on depth information from rendered images of a visualization system. The virtual sensor can output data which simulates some ultrasonic transducer or LIDAR scanner.

Creanex simulator platform supports alternatives to create virtual sensors:

- Simulation signals.
- Simulation of data streams a sensor is transmitting.
- Configurable IO channels which measure state of the machine parts.

The first two are fixed implementations in the simulation model or special interfaces the simulator platform supports. For example, the simulation model can have output signals, which contain information calculated from the objects in scene. The simulation signals are connected to selected IO channels via configuration as shown in Figure 6 on page 14.

The third alternative for virtual sensors is that the state of machine's kinematic structure can be made available as IO channels to simulate sensors. In so called *ObjectStateChannels* configuration it is possible to create simulated sensors for several machine part characteristics: position, velocity, orientation and joint values. First the IO context and object channels are named and then according to named sections the channels are configured to measure selected kinematic attributes of a machine. For example, the following configuration snippet creates IO channels which have the X, Y and Z coordinates for the machine part which is named in the simulation model as *PartName*.

```
[IOChannelNames]
IODeviceName = MachineModel
*State = MachineFramePosition
```

```
[MachineFramePosition]
Type = MachinePartPosition
Name = PartName
```

5 Virtual feedback visualization concepts

In the following sections visualization concepts are presented that are identified for each use case.

5.1 Visualization examples for augmented information

There are several techniques how to add augmented information to rendered 3D graphics. There can be symbols as 3D objects or lines made of piecewise linear 3D tubes. Adding 3D objects like humans can be used to enrich scenarios for collision avoidance test cases.

Laser projector and rotatable spotlight are promising technologies that are foreseen to be used for providing XR content for a work machine operator. Two 3D graphics technics are presented how laser projection and spotlight can be simulated in 3D graphics.

5.1.1 Laser projection with decals

The High-Definition Render Pipeline (HDRP) in Unity includes the Decal Projector component, which allows projection of specific Materials (pictures) into the Scene. When the Decal Projector component projects decals into the Scene, they interact with the Scene's lighting and wrap around Meshes. You can use thousands of decals in your Scene simultaneously. This means that the rendering process is not resource intensive if the decals use the same Material [1].

For example, a bitmap used as the material of a decal is in Figure 21 and the result when the decal projector wraps the material along the ground surface is presented in Figure 22.

Figure 21: Bitmap used in a material.

Figure 22: Decal projector wraps a material on ground surface.

The decal projector can also be used to draw virtual *laser* lines along the ground surface. In Figure 23 two thick lines have been projected on excavated work site.

Figure 23: Projected lines along ground surface.

A decal projector can be used as a virtual equivalent of a laser projector. For example, in UC1, projected decals can highlight the outer borders of previously groomed slope lanes on the ground, so that operators can estimate the right overlap and work more efficiently. In UC3, decals may be used to project the edges of a planned trench on the ground, allowing operators to work precisely even when the original (chalk or spray) markings on the real soil have been torn up or covered by dirt. Both of these visualizations will also be embedded in their respective task scenario context within deliverable D3.7.

5.1.2 Spotlight

A spotlight emits light from a specified location and range over which the light diminishes. The spotlight constrains the light it emits to an angle, which results in a cone-shaped region of illumination. Light may also diminish at the edges of the spotlight's cone. Increasing a spot angle increases the width of the cone.

A spotlight has an emitting location and direction, which can be controlled by simulation. In Figure 24 a spotlight is shown in slightly foggy weather condition, so the cone of the light is also visible. Spotlight may have almost any colour, even black.

Figure 24: Spotlight.

The spotlight can be used in use cases to highlight detected obstacles and/or persons in the vicinity of the work machine.

5.1.3 LED bars

The concept of windscreen LED bars can be simulated by 3D graphics objects. A 3D tube can be modelled to be around the windscreen edges and along it another 3D object simulating LED lights can be placed and moved. The LED bar added to the excavator cabin model and close-up screen capture of the LED lights are shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Simulated LED bar

The simulation parameters of the LED bar are configured in a text file:

- Number of LEDs and indices of the corner LEDs
- Name of the parent object
- Coordinate points of the path relative to the parent object.
- Number of activated LEDs based on distance.

LED bar can be added to different machine simulations easy just by creating a 3D model of the bar and then writing the configuration accordingly.

5.1.4 Camera stream

Creanex simulator platform supports virtual video streams that are based on Real-Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP), which a network protocol used to control multimedia streaming particularly for video and audio. The video streaming feature was integrated to be part of the excavator simulator to have a tool for testing video inputs if needed in the final demonstrator. In Figure 26 the visual system of the excavator simulator is generating virtual RTSP video stream from address 127.0.0.1/TopCamera and played by VLC media player application.

Figure 26: Virtual RTSP video stream.

The simulator generated virtual camera stream has been tested with the detection algorithm implemented by TUD. Screen capture of the detection result is shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27: Detecting persons from the camera stream generated by the simulator.

5.2 Use case 1

5.2.1 Snow groomer simulation

Snow groomer simulation is based on the Creanex simulator platform. Virtual working environment, the simulation scene, has been created from real slope data provided by Prinoth in LandXml format modelling the surface of one slope at Ladurns ski resort. The 3D slope model and a screen capture from Google Earth application, which gives a reference view of the area, are shown in Figure 28. The slope model was imported into the open-source 3D modelling software Blender¹ and surrounding land scape was built from freely available satellite point-cloud data². The Blender model was exported to fbx file and imported to visual application which is based on Unity gaming engine. The scene can be interpreted

¹ <https://www.blender.org/>

² https://www.opendem.info/opendemeu_download_highres.html

to be a digital twin of the real environment. The model in Blender tool and screen capture from the simulator visual application are shown in Figure 29.

Figure 28: Ladurns LandXml model and overall view of the ski resort area

Figure 29: Terrain model in Blender tool and capture from Unity visualization.

In Figure 30 the view of the cabin is shown in three different lightning conditions: clear day, foggy day and night. In the night view the machine cabin and driving lights are switched on.

Figure 30: Snow groomer cabin view and examples of lightning conditions.

5.2.2 Control of the snow groomer simulator

The snow groomer simulator is controlled by CAN messages received from the Prinoth cabin controls:

- The two levers on the left-hand side controls the tracks.
- The multifunction joystick on the right hand-side controls the front bulldozer blade and the rear tiller.

A general description of CAN interfaces supported in Creanex simulators is presented in the section 3.1.2 on page 15. The received commands from CAN messages are configured to be connected to simulation signals, which are the interface of the simulation model as shown in Figure 31. Two virtual CANOpen nodes were configured: *JoystickNode* and *SnowGroomerCANnode*. The nodes are connected to two different CAN buses. *JoystickNode* receives messages from the right hand-side multifunction joystick and a push button panel. *SnowGroomerCANnode* sends simulated sensor data and receives CAN messages of the track controls sent by application running in TTC ECU or alternatively directly from the track control levers.

Figure 31: Snow groomer simulator signal, IO and CAN interfaces.

The simulation signals are fixed in the simulation implementation, but the connection to IO channels is configurable in a text file. The control signals of the snow groomer simulation model are

- IN_TrackLeft
- IN_TrackRight
- IN_BladeArmLift
- IN_BladeRoll
- IN_BladeTilt
- IN_BladeTurn
- IN_BladeSideLeft
- IN_BladeSideRight
- IN_TillerArmTilt
- IN_TillerArmTurn
- IN_TillerFrameRoll
- IN_TillerFrameTilt
- IN_TillerFrameTurn
- IN_TillerTilt
- IN_TillerBlade
- IN_TillerFlapLeft
- IN_TillerFlapRight
- IN_PositionLights
- IN_LowBeamLights
- IN_HighBeamLights
- IN_SearchLight

The control signals get their input from the IO channels of the virtual CANopen nodes.

5.2.3 Virtual sensors of the snow groomer simulator

The snow groomer simulation is configured to provide virtual IO channels measuring the dynamic state properties of the machine body. The IO context was named *SnowGroomerModel* and has the following IO channels:

- MachineFramePosition-X
- MachineFramePosition-Y
- MachineFramePosition-Z
- MachineFrameOrientation-Yaw
- MachineFrameSpeed-VX
- MachineFrameGyro-WZ

The IO channels of the simulation models are further routed to IO channels of the CANopen node *SnowGroomerCANnode*, which send the data as CAN messages. The specification of the object dictionary and structure of CAN messages are shown in Figure 32.

COB ID	Byte 1	Byte 2	Byte 3	Byte 4	Byte 5	Byte 6	Byte 7	Byte 8
0x190	0x5010Sub1			0x5010Sub2				
0x290	0x5010Sub3				0x5010Sub4		0x5010Sub5	
0x291	0x5010Sub6							
0x390	0x5020Sub1		0x5020Sub2		0x5020Sub3		0x5020Sub4	
0x391	0x5020Sub5		0x5020Sub6		0x5020Sub7		0x5020Sub8	
Object entry	Function		Datatype	Unit				
0x5010Sub1	MachineFramePosition-X		REAL32	Meters				
0x5010Sub2	MachineFramePosition-Y		REAL32	Meters				
0x5010Sub3	MachineFramePosition-Z		REAL32	Meters				
0x5010Sub4	MachineHeading		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5010Sub5	MachineSpeed		INT16	1 m/s = 1000 in CAN				
0x5010Sub6	MachineGyro-WZ		INT16	1 degree/s = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub1	ObjectHeading-1		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub2	ObjectDistance-1		UINT16	1 m = 10 in CAN				
0x5020Sub3	ObjectHeading-2		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub4	ObjectDistance-2		UINT16	1 m = 10 in CAN				
0x5020Sub3	ObjectHeading-2		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub4	ObjectDistance-2		UINT16	1 m = 10 in CAN				
0x5020Sub5	ObjectHeading-3		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub6	ObjectDistance-3		UINT16	1 m = 10 in CAN				
0x5020Sub7	ObjectHeading-4		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub8	ObjectDistance-4		UINT16	1 m = 10 in CAN				

Figure 32: *SnowGroomerCANnode* object dictionary and CAN messages.

The position coordinates are sent to CAN bus as 32-bit real numbers, so there is no need to do scaling for them. The yaw angle of the frame and velocities are sent as 16-bit signed integers and scaled to maintain appropriate resolution.

In addition of the machine body measurements the simulator sends information of objects in the vicinity of the machine. The simulation model contains the heading angle and distance signals for the four closest objects. Names of the object detection signals are

- OUT_DetectedObject1_Heading
- OUT_DetectedObject1_Distance

- OUT_DetectedObject2_Heading
- OUT_DetectedObject2_Distance
- OUT_DetectedObject3_Heading
- OUT_DetectedObject3_Distance
- OUT_DetectedObject4_Heading
- OUT_DetectedObject4_Distance

The scaling of the values and the connection to IO channels is configurable in a text file. The heading and distance values are scaled, so that angle in degrees is multiplied by 100 and the distance in meters is multiplied by 10. This way a signed 16-bit integer represents the value having sufficiently good resolution and data from two objects can fit into one CAN message.

5.2.4 Feedback concepts for snow groomer operator

In deliverable D2.2 three snow groomer scenarios are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The scenarios are

1. build slope matching target surface,
2. obstacle avoidance and
3. zero sight navigation.

The scenarios are divided into tasks and requirements of each task are analysed. Based on the requirements useful feedback concepts have been identified to help the operator to more effectively

- navigate to the target area,
- have clear picture where the vehicle is relative to the target area,
- see progress of the work,
- monitor vehicle path and groom parallel lanes precisely,
- see deviation between the actual and target surfaces,
- avoid obstacles or skiers.

The feedback visualization concepts envisioned in the use case 1, snow groomer, are presented in Figure 33:

- dash lines to indicate snow height,
- shield width lines on both sides to highlight grooming lanes,
- area restriction lines,
- route navigation lines,
- object highlight by a light spot,
- indicator light matrix on side or bottom edges of the cabin to show deviation between actual and target surfaces.

Figure 33: Concept ideas for use case 1 feedback and visualization.

Three feedback concept ideas have been implemented for the snow groomer simulator:

- spotlight
- laser projection
- LED bars on windscreen

5.2.4.1 Virtual spotlight

A virtual spotlight was added to the snow groomer model and mounted on the machine frame. The concept is proposed by PRIN and TUG. The spotlight is in the middle of the top front edge of the cabin. In the real machine the spotlight is manually controlled by a handle, Figure 34. The on and off state of the light is controlled by the simulation signal *IN_SearchLight*.

Figure 34: Spotlight mounted on the cabin roof.

The direction of the light can be controlled by two IO channels. Currently the control is implemented by temporary testing IO, which are manually adjusted. *SpotLightRotY* controls tilting and *SpotLightRotZ* controls direction. Simulation signals can be easily added, so that the control could be done for example by a CAN message.

In Figure 35 the spotlight is in operation and highlights a skier which is approaching the snow groomer.

Figure 35: Spotlight highlights a skier.

5.2.4.2 Virtual laser projection

Laser projection can be simulated by decals, which are bitmaps projected on the simulated scene. The laser projection concept has been proposed by TUG and can be used for multiple feedback functions. In simulation the focus was on helping navigation to the target area. The selected simulation method was adding a feature which contains a set of decals placed on configured location in the simulated scene. Below is an example snippet of the configuration and the bitmaps used for the waypoint and goal decals are shown in Figure 36. For each decal there are seven parameters: X, Y and Z coordinates, direction angle, width and height.

```
[Decals]
*Decal = TUG_Waypoint 1150.00 -1082.12 613.51 1.8 2.00 1.07
*Decal = TUG_Waypoint 1145.08 -1067.50 614.82 1.8 2.00 1.07
*Decal = TUG_Waypoint 1141.06 -1051.70 615.57 1.9 2.00 1.07
*Decal = TUG_Goal 1137.03 -1039.80 615.05 0.98 3.00 3.00
```


Figure 36: Bitmaps used for waypoint and goal decals.

A decal in scene is shown when it is in front of the machine, so that the imaginary laser projector on the roof of the machine can project the image, Figure 37.

Figure 37: Laser projected waypoints in night and day light conditions.

5.2.4.3 Virtual LED bars on the snow groomer windscreen

3D model of the LED bar was added on the windscreen of the snow groomer model. The LED bar can be used for multiple feedback functions, for example to visualize how precisely the machine is grooming parallel lanes or to inform deviation between the actual and target surfaces. In simulation the focus was to implement a feature which informs about skiers in the vicinity on the machine.

Animated skiers are added to the test scenario using a tool that defines the skier's route. There can be multiple skiers having their own route and speed. In Figure 38 the designed routes in a saved test scenario are shown by red lines.

Figure 38: Skiers' route in a test scenario.

Position of the skiers relative to the machine is supervised and the virtual LEDs are activated on the bar accordingly. In Figure 39 a skier is approaching the machine from the left side and the operator is warned by activated red lights on the left side of the windscreen. The closer the skier is the more LEDs are activated.

Figure 39: LED bar on the windscreen warns of a skier on left side.

5.3 Use case 2

VTT developed the reach stacker simulator for low fidelity testing of XR features and there has not been any need for further development of the simulation since the first version of the deliverable the D4.5, so the section 5.3.1 - 5.3.2 are same as before.

5.3.1 Reachstacker simulation

The reachstacker simulation is developed by VTT. The simulated scenario is container handling in a harbour area, Figure 40.

Figure 40: Reach stacker in simulated working environment.

The reach stacker can be operated from the cabin of the machine or from a remote station. The simulation supports both, but focus is more on the remote operation using camera views. The operator follows multiple camera streams simultaneously and observes how the container approaches the landing point on e.g., a truck or another stack of containers and how it settles in place.

In simulation the rendering camera showing a view can be freely positioned in the world or mounted on a machine part. One typical camera setup is to mount it inside a cabin looking forward in driving direction and then the camera moves with the machine. The camera can also be programmed to follow an object automatically keeping it in sight. The shown augmented information can be customized to function the way found most useful in different setups.

A setup was created on which user can choose between four different camera views:

- 1) cabin view/driver's perspective with route navigation indication, Figure 41.
- 2) spreader top-down view, Figure 42
- 3) rear view/counterweight and obstacle tracking, Figure 43
- 4) cabin or spreader view with load charts, Figure 44

Figure 41: Reachstacker AR guidance system: vehicle path and pick up/placement locations.

Figure 42: Reachstacker AR guidance system: twist lock/corner positions, centre line, and tipping axis.

Figure 43: Reachstacker AR guidance system: counterweight safety area and obstacle tracking.

Figure 44: Reachstacker AR guidance system: load charts.

More details of UI concepts, user evaluations and videos are presented in *Deliverable 3.4 – Low-Fidelity XR Prototypes (First Version)*.

5.3.2 Feedback concepts for reachstacker operator

In deliverable D2.2 three logistics scenarios are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The scenarios are

1. pick a container from the stack,
2. place a container to the stack,
3. pick a container from ground,
4. place a container on ground,
5. pick a container from the trailer and
6. place a container to the trailer.

The scenarios are divided into tasks and requirements of each task are analysed. Based on the requirements useful feedback concepts have been identified to help the operator to more effectively

- navigate to a container which is ordered to be picked up,

- position the spreader precisely relative to the container and to ensure the container can be grasped safely,
- see that twist locks are locked properly before the container is lifted,
- see that twist locks are fully open when spreader is lifted off the container,
- see that the container is precisely above where it is placed on,
- identify dangerous situations in time like humans in near vicinity or stability risks,
- see the weight distribution of the container,
- avoid collisions.

The feedback visualization concepts envisioned in the use case 2, logistics, are presented in Figure 45:

- virtual load chart and container location on it,
- lines for allowable operation area,
- highlight of corner pin positions and weight on them,
- indication of centre of mass
- indication distance to container
- object recognition and highlight,
- route navigation,
- spreader status indication and orientation relative to container.

Figure 45: Concept ideas for use case 2 feedback and visualization.

5.4 Use case 3

5.4.1 Excavator simulation

Excavator simulation is based on Creanex simulator platform. The simulated is a wheeled excavator, such as the TUD test machine is. A larger tracked excavator can also be used. The virtual environment shown in Figure 46 is an artificial construction site with an area for excavation.

Figure 46: Excavator in simulated working environment.

For different demonstrations or evaluation tests the controls of the excavator can be configured as required. The CAN bus interface can be configured using the CANopen device configuration files. It is also possible to use any gaming joysticks having the Windows DirectX interface or any analogue joysticks connected using Creanex IO cards.

The surface of the earth is simulated in such a way that a hole or a ditch can be excavated (Figure 47).

Figure 47: Excavator cabin view and excavatable soil.

A test scenario can be saved in a file, so the same situation can be simulated multiple times and results can be compared between operations. The excavation task can be defined by a shape object which is added to the scenario and placed under the ground surface. In Figure 48 the added shape of the excavation target surface is a box having inclined sides

Figure 48: Target shape and placing it in excavation scenario.

5.4.2 Control of the excavator simulator

For different demonstrations or evaluation tests the controls of the excavator can be configured as required. The CAN bus interface can be configured using the CANopen device configuration files. It is also possible to use any gaming joysticks having the Windows DirectX interface or any analogue joysticks connected using Creanex IO cards.

A configuration has been developed to support the TUD's cabin mock-up, in which both the Danfoss joysticks and the XR elements developed by TUD are connected by CAN. The CAN messages are sent and received by virtual CANnodes, CAN message frames are mapped to IO channels, which are connected to simulation signals as shown in Figure 49. Two virtual CANopen nodes were configured: *JoystickMsgReader* and *ExcavatorCANnode*. The nodes are connected to two different CAN buses. *JoystickMsgReader* receives messages from Danfoss joysticks. *ExcavatorCANnode* sends simulated sensor data to TUD system.

Figure 49: Excavator simulator signal and CAN interfaces.

The simulation signals are fixed in the simulation implementation, but the connection to IO channels is configurable in a text file. The control signals of the excavator simulation model are

- IN_Steering
- IN_GasPedal
- IN_BrakePedal
- IN_ParkingBrake
- IN_DirectionForward
- IN_DirectionReverse
- IN_CreepSpeed
- IN_TurnPlatform
- IN_LiftBoom
- IN_TiltStick
- IN_LiftLeftLeg
- IN_LiftRightLeg
- IN_LiftShield

The control signals get their input from the IO channels of the virtual CANopen nodes.

5.4.3 Virtual sensors of the excavator simulator

The excavator simulation is configured to provide virtual IO channels measuring the dynamic state properties of the machine body. The IO context was named *ExcavatorModel* and has the following IO channels:

- BucketPosition-X
- BucketPosition -Y
- BucketPosition -Z
- BucketOrientation-Roll (rotation around X-axis)
- BucketOrientation-Pitch (rotation around y-axis)
- BucketOrientation-Yaw (rotation around Z-axis)

In addition of the machine body measurements the simulator sends information of bucket and target surface inclination angles, distance between bucket and target and heading and distance of the four closest objects in the vicinity of the machine. Names of the output signals are

- OUT_BucketInclination
- OUT_TargetInclination
- OUT_BucketDistanceToTarget
- OUT_DetectedObject1_Heading
- OUT_DetectedObject1_Distance
- OUT_DetectedObject2_Heading
- OUT_DetectedObject2_Distance
- OUT_DetectedObject3_Heading
- OUT_DetectedObject3_Distance
- OUT_DetectedObject4_Heading
- OUT_DetectedObject4_Distance

If the target is not below the bucket edge, the distance measurement is 100.0.

The values of detected object heading and distance are zero, if the object is not detected.

The IO channels of the simulation models are further routed to IO channels of the CANopen node *ExcavatorCANnode*, which send the data as CAN messages. The specification of the object dictionary and structure of CAN messages are shown in Figure 50.

COB ID	Byte 1	Byte 2	Byte 3	Byte 4	Byte 5	Byte 6	Byte 7	Byte 8
0x190	0x5010Sub1				0x5010Sub2			
0x191	0x5010Sub3				0x5010Sub4			
0x192	0x5010Sub5				0x5010Sub6			
0x290	0x5010Sub7		0x5010Sub8		0x5010Sub9			
0x390	0x5020Sub1		0x5020Sub2		0x5020Sub3		0x5020Sub4	
0x391	0x5020Sub5		0x5020Sub6		0x5020Sub7		0x5020Sub8	
Object entry	Function		Datatype	Unit				
0x5010Sub1	BucketPosition-X		REAL32	Meters				
0x5010Sub2	BucketPosition-Y		REAL32	Meters				
0x5010Sub3	BucketPosition-Z		REAL32	Meters				
0x5010Sub4	BucketOrientation RotX		REAL32	Degrees				
0x5010Sub5	BucketOrientation RotY		REAL32	Degrees				
0x5010Sub6	BucketOrientation RotZ		REAL32	Degrees				
0x5010Sub7	BucketInclination		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5010Sub8	TargetSurfaceInclination		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5010Sub8	BucketDistanceToTarget		INT16	1 m = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub1	ObjectHeading-1		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub2	ObjectDistance-1		UINT16	1 m = 10 in CAN				
0x5020Sub3	ObjectHeading-2		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub4	ObjectDistance-2		UINT16	1 m = 10 in CAN				
0x5020Sub5	ObjectHeading-3		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub6	ObjectDistance-3		UINT16	1 m = 10 in CAN				
0x5020Sub7	ObjectHeading-4		INT16	1 degree = 100 in CAN				
0x5020Sub8	ObjectDistance-4		UINT16	1 m = 10 in CAN				

Figure 50: Excavator object dictionary and CAN messages.

The position coordinates and orientation angles are sent to CAN bus as 32-bit real numbers, so there is no need to do scaling for them. Less resolution is required for the inclination angles and data of detected objects, so they are sent as 16-bit integers and scaled to maintain appropriate resolution.

5.4.4 Feedback concepts for excavator operator

In deliverable D2.2 three excavator scenarios are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The scenarios are

1. finish grading,
2. collision avoidance and
3. infield design.

The scenarios are divided into tasks and requirements of each task are analysed. Based on the requirements useful feedback concepts have been identified to help the operator to more effectively

- see that the reference height is set correctly,
- assess the alignment between real environment and digital model of the target,
- deviation between the actual and target surfaces,
- plan the work,
- identify dangerous situations in time like humans in near vicinity or stability risks and
- avoid collisions.

The feedback visualization concept envisioned in use case 3, excavator, are presented in Figure 51.

- target depth indication,
- difference to target height,
- work area indication and planning,
- Object detection, warning, and highlighting.

Figure 51: Concept ideas for use case 3 feedback and visualization.

Three feedback concept ideas have been implemented for the excavator simulator:

- Matrix display showing difference between bucket and target surface.
- Laser projection
- LED bars on windscreen.

5.4.4.1 Virtual depth monitor mounted on the stick boom

A depth monitor display is mounted on the excavator stick boom based on concept proposed by TUD., see Figure 57. While the operator's gaze focuses on the bucket, the relative position of the bucket to the target surface is simultaneously visible. In the simulator implementation the blue line is the bucket edge relative to the gravity and the orange line is the target surface inclination relative to gravity below the bucket. The lines get closer to each other when the bucket approaches the target surface, and the lines are inclined if the bucket edge or the target surface are not horizontal.

Figure 52: Depth monitor mounted on the stick boom.

The depth monitor has five different modes depending how the bucket and the target surface are relative to each other. Examples of the modes are shown in Figure 53 and described in Table 2.

Figure 53: Depth monitor modes.

Mode	Description
A	Bucket is above target level
B	Bucket is slightly above target level
C	Bucket is at target level
D	Bucket is slightly below target level
E	Bucket is below target level

Table 2: Depth monitor modes

5.4.4.2 Virtual laser projection

Laser projection can be used for multiple feedback functions. In simulation two cases have been considered: highlighting a drainpipe and edges of the excavation target area. The simulated concepts do not exactly simulate a laser projector mounted on the machine, for example on the cabin roof. Decals, which are used to simulate the laser projector, are projected from close distance from the terrain surface, so the projection is not visible on the boom or bucket if the projection is behind them.

A drainpipe can be added and buried into the simulation scene. In Figure 54 the drainpipe is highlighted by red line projected on the ground surface on top of the pipe.

Figure 54: Drainpipe highlighted by simulated laser projection.

Another implemented feedback by projection is highlighting the edges of the excavation target area.

Figure 55: Edges of the excavation area highlighted by simulated laser projection.

5.4.4.3 Virtual LED bars on the excavator windscreen

3D model of the LED bar was added on the windscreen of the excavator model. The LED bar can be used for multiple feedback functions, for example to visualize stability by showing warning, if support legs loose contact, or to inform deviation between the actual and target surfaces. In simulation the focus was to implement a feature which informs about workers in the vicinity on the machine.

An animated worker was added to the visualization media, and it can be added to the test scenario saved in a file. A walking route can be defined along which the worker walks at defined speed. The worker and route planning view are presented in Figure 56.

Figure 56: Animated worker and its walking route in excavation scenario.

Position of the worker relative to the machine is supervised and the virtual LEDs are activated on the bar accordingly. In Figure 57 a worker is approaching the machine from the right side and the operator is warned by activated red lights on the right side of the windscreen. The closer the worker is the more LEDs are activated.

Figure 57: LED bar on the windscreen warns of a worker on the right side.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the concept of virtual user interface and how simulators can and are being used in development and testing. Using virtual control panels, the simulator is cost effectively taken in use without first investing on hardware platform. To be able to show more information new sensors and environment data models are needed based on which new information is derived and made visible. In simulated environment the data exist in the model and can be made available for systems under development.

The 3D graphics technics decal projection and spotlight can be used to simulate augmented visual effects that have foreseen to be tested in the THEIA^{XR} project. Decal projection can be used to add symbols and lines on terrain surface. Spotlight can have different colours and used to highlight objects. Additional 3D models can be added to the simulated machine to provide more information for the operator. New concepts the depth monitor and the LED bars developed in THEIA^{XR} are good examples.

Three different simulators are presented, one for each use case. The UC1 snow groomer and the UC3 excavator simulators are developed by CREA and based on Creanex simulator platform. Simulation of the snow groomer was developed in the project and for the excavator CREA had an earlier version, which has further developed to fulfil THEIA^{XR} requirements. The UC2 simulator of reach stacker was developed by VTT.

In the deliverable *D2.2 Technology analysis and requirements specification (first version)* scenarios are described including specifications where XR technologies can improve the workflow. The scenarios are divided into tasks and based on analysed requirements feedback concepts have been identified to help the operator to do the work more effectively and safely. The concepts of the feedback visualizations, which are foreseen to be added to simulations were presented for each use case.

The focus is on user interactions with the simulated machine operating in a virtual environment. The simulated functions and information design of the virtual user interface and simulators are shaped by the transdisciplinary co-design process (tasks T3.2 and T3.3), where planned features and information elements are scrutinized, co-designed and validated in collaboration with vehicle operators. The results of T3.2 contributed to the development and design of the simulators now that the technological frameworks are in place. The virtual environments and simulations together with the cabin mockup presented in the deliverable *D5.5 Multimodal immersive cockpit* are envisioned to allow evaluation and prototyping of simulated feedback modalities beyond the cabin environment. The simulations and the THEIA^{XR} concepts developed for the use cases provide a virtual platform for testing, evaluation and demonstration.

References

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

AR	Augmented Reality
CAN	Controller Area Network
DCF	Device Configuration File
CiA	CAN in Automation
DOF	Degrees of Freedom
ECU	Embedded Control Unit
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HDM	Head-mounted Display
HIL	Hardware in the loop
NMEA	National Marine Electronics Association
PWM	Pulse width modulated
SIL	Software in the loop
UDP	User Datagram Protocoll
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	eXtended Reality